

Influence of the Precursor Composition on the Resulting Absorber Properties and Defect Concentration in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$ Absorbers

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Supporting Information

Figure S1. Compositions of the added historic samples for larger statistics.

The added historic samples were produced before the series discussed in the manuscript. They serve the purpose of viewing a larger database and confirming the presence of general trends similar to the trends observed in the analyzed sample series.

Figure S2. Analyzed five small (approx. $5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$) samples, left to right: A703 – A706 – A709 – A728 – A712. CZTSe absorbers with varied Sn-content on 3 mm SLG/Mo substrates.

Table S1. Composition of various samples with different Sn content in the precursors. Nominal precursor compositions are estimated from the sputtering duration. Both EDX and XRF data confirm the similar Cu/Sn ratio for all the absorbers (also see Figure S2 and Figure 1).

Precursor	Sample	Substrate	Zn_a/CuSn/Sn/Zn_b	Cu (at.%)	Zn(at.%)	Sn (at.%)	Cu/Sn	Cu/(Zn+Sn)	Zn/Sn	
	A703	Z928	324/1625/0/44	44.7	36.1	19.2	2.33	0.81	1.88	
	A706	Z977	324/1625/81/44	43.1	34.8	22.1	1.95	0.76	1.58	
	A709	Z984	324/1625/162/44	41.7	33.6	24.8	1.68	0.71	1.36	
	A728	Z992	324/1625/243/44	40.3	32.5	27.3	1.48	0.67	1.19	
	A712	Z996	324/1625/324/44	39.0	31.4	29.6	1.31	0.64	1.06	
EDX	Sample	Substrate	Zn1/CuSn/Sn/Zn2	Cu (at.%)	Zn (at.%)	Sn (at.%)	Cu/Sn	Cu/(Zn+Sn)	Zn/Sn	
	A703	Z928	324/1625/0/44	40.2	33.5	26.3	1.53	0.67	1.27	
	A706	Z977	324/1625/81/44	40.9	33.8	25.2	1.62	0.69	1.34	
	A709	Z984	324/1625/162/44	41.1	32.1	26.9	1.53	0.70	1.20	
	A728	Z992	324/1625/243/44	40.8	32.7	26.6	1.53	0.69	1.23	
	A712	Z996	324/1625/324/44	39.9	33.3	26.9	1.48	0.66	1.24	
XRF	Sample	Substrate	Zn1/CuSn/Sn/Zn2	Cu (at.%)	Zn (at.%)	Sn (at.%)	Cu/Sn	Cu/(Zn+Sn)	Zn/Sn	
	A703	Z928	324/1625/0/44	40.8	33.7	25.5	1.60	0.69	1.32	
	A706	Z977	324/1625/81/44	40.3	34.2	25.6	1.58	0.67	1.34	
	A709	Z984	324/1625/162/44	41.0	32.7	26.3	1.56	0.70	1.25	
	A728	Z992	324/1625/243/44	40.6	32.5	26.9	1.51	0.68	1.21	
	A712	Z996	324/1625/324/44	40.1	32.3	27.6	1.46	0.67	1.17	
	Big samples (30x30 mm²)									
	A705		324/1625/0/44	38.3	33.7	28.1	1.36	0.62	1.20	
A707		324/1625/81/44	37.7	34.2	28.2	1.34	0.60	1.21		

Figure S3. Precursor and absorber composition in ternary composition diagram. Samples with different starting precursor compositions finally reach a similar absorber composition region due to the Sn-related composition shift during the annealing process.

Figure S4. Mapping of the relative intensity of ZnSe Raman peak in two big samples: left - A705 ($Cu/Sn_{Precursor} = 2.33$), right - A707 ($Cu/Sn_{Precursor} = 1.95$). Outermost pixels of the maps include edge effects due to partial covering of the substrate's surface during deposition by sample holders/masks.

Figure S5. Mapping of the relative intensity of CuSe Raman peak in two big samples: left - A705 ($\text{Cu/Sn}_{\text{Precursor}} = 2.33$), right - A707 ($\text{Cu/Sn}_{\text{Precursor}} = 1.95$).

Figure S6. Relative intensity of the Raman peaks associated to $[\text{V}_{\text{Cu}} + \text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}]$ cluster defects versus Cu/Sn ratio measured in the absorber by XRF.

This trend was further evaluated by an analysis of the PL band maximum (Figure S11). Again, the samples show largely overlapping final Cu/Sn ratios and fail to explain the shifted PL maximum by more than 20 meV and the improved QY that was shown in the main manuscript in Figure 7.

Figure S7. PL band maximum versus Cu/Sn ratio measured in the absorber.

Figure S8. Correlation of the PL band maximum with the relative intensity of the LO peak close to 250 cm^{-1} in the Raman spectra measured under 785 nm excitation wavelength.

Figure S9. (a) Representative EQE spectrum and (b) IV curve for the + 81 s sample with a Cu/Sn ratio in the precursor of 1.95.

Correlation with final composition

First, the precursor composition has been correlated with the final composition measured by XRF (Figure S8). This allowed to define a clear trend in the evolution of the Cu/Sn ratio measured in the absorber with change of this ratio calculated for different precursors. However, the XRF measured range of Cu/Sn values in the final compositions, i.e., approximately 1.46 to 1.60 for the whole dataset, is significantly smaller than in the precursor with a range from 1.31 to 2.33. Similar values were measured by EDX, a range of Cu/Sn from 1.48 to 1.62 is covered by all the samples included in the series, corroborating the XRF results. This allows to conclude that a compositional shift during the annealing takes place and results in a narrow range for the final compositions from both Cu-rich or Cu-poor precursors, either due to the incorporation of Sn via SnSe_{2-x} vapor from the external Sn-wire which is always supplied during the annealing or via evaporation of excess SnSe_{2-x} from the forming absorber layer. In either case no Sn-Se related secondary phases were found at the absorber surface by Raman analysis. Note, that no change of the Cu/Zn ratio is expected in the precursor, it is (not shown in Table 1) 1.23 ± 0.05 for EDX and 1.23 ± 0.03 for XRF measured values. This is in good agreement with the calculated precursor Cu/Zn value which is 1.24 for all samples.

Figure S10. Cu/Sn ratio measured in the absorber by XRF versus Cu/Sn ratio calculated in the precursor from the expected thickness of Cu and Sn layers.

Considering the observed trend in the variation of the final composition, the measured cation ratios were correlated with the Raman and PL results presented in the main manuscript Figures 6 - 8. Further, the relative intensity of the ZnSe Raman peak is correlated with the Zn/Sn ratio (Figure S9). Usually, an appearance of the ZnSe or ZnS secondary phase when growing kesterites is strongly linked with the Zn/Sn ratio, and a clear threshold can be defined in the latter value after which a high amount of these secondary phases is observed in kesterite thin films.^[1] This tendency is confirmed in the first four samples (with precursor Cu/Sn ratios from 2.33 to 1.48) for which a threshold at Zn/Sn \approx 1.27 (in the final absorber) can be defined. However, the sample with a precursor Cu/Sn ratio of 1.31 (and a final Zn/Sn \approx 1.20) is outside of this trend exhibiting high amounts of ZnSe with Zn/Sn ratio lower than the identified threshold. This can be related to the distribution of ZnSe phase in the layer which may be present mainly at the surface of the sample,

or to the significant difference in the starting alloy configuration and hence formation paths (comparatively high amount and therefore large contribution of secondary phases during the CZTSe formation) comparing to other samples. Thus, a direct comparison of this aspect for all samples appears to be difficult from this point of view.

Figure S11. Relative intensity of the ZnSe Raman peak versus Zn/Sn ratio measured in the absorber by XRF.

Following the analogy discussed in the context of Figure 6b, the relative defect concentration $[V_{Cu} + Zn_{Cu}]$ vs the Cu/Sn ratio in the final absorber is shown in Figure S10. For the samples corresponding to precursors with Cu/Sn = 2.33 to 1.68 (black, red, and blue symbols) a broad final composition overlapping region around Cu/Sn between 1.50 to 1.65 is visible. A notable difference in the relative defect content is present, however, a clear trend in the relative defect content with the Cu/Sn content in the absorber cannot be established.

- [1] E. Grau-Luque, I. Anefnaf, N. Benhaddou, R. Fonoll-Rubio, I. Becerril-Romero, S. Aazou, E. Saucedo, Z. Sekkat, A. Perez-Rodriguez, V. Izquierdo-Roca and M. Guc, “Combinatorial and machine learning approaches for the analysis of $Cu_2ZnGeSe_4$: influence of the off-stoichiometry on defect formation and solar cell performance,” *J. Mater. Chem. A*, vol. 9, no. 16, pp. 10466–10476, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D1TA01299A.